

A COMMUNITY-INFORMED REPORT

Faith in Practice

Co-producing Health Priorities with LGBTQI+ People of Faith

Future research priorities and early findings, set by participants themselves.

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Executive summary

Faith in Practice: Co-Producing Health Priorities with LGBTQI+ People of Faith asked LGBTQI+ people of faith what NHS healthcare research at the intersection of these identities should focus on, how it should be designed to be most accessible, and what they want it to lead to.

NHS healthcare experiences as an LGBTQI+ person, and as a person of faith, are reasonably well documented in their own right. The experience of being both at once, in the same clinical encounter, is not. The project ran two online focus groups, supplemented by one-to-one conversations and written submissions, with participants from Christian, Jewish, Muslim, Sikh, Pagan and other worldviews and traditions, across a wide range of LGBTQI+ identities. Most participants carried further intersecting minoritised identities, including disability, chronic illness, racialisation, migration history, neurodivergence and HIV status.

Across both groups, participants described healthcare environments tending to recognise one of their identities at a time, and treating the other as either incompatible with the first, irrelevant to clinical care, or a problem for the patient to manage. Six themes recurred:

- **Sexual and reproductive health.** The most discussed clinical area in both groups, and the one where the intersection was most visible. NHS sexual health services were described as configured around heterosexual couples and gay men, leaving lesbian, bisexual and queer women, including women of faith specifically, without an operational frame. Religious framings of sex were often unable to be discussed with clinicians at all, leaving participants to construct their own understanding of safe sexual practice. Participants described visible markers of faith, such as the hijab, triggering assumptions that closed off sexual history conversations entirely.
- **The burden of self-advocacy.** Participants described doing the work of being seen as both queer and a person of faith in every clinical encounter. The advocacy was often double: explaining their queerness to faith-aware clinicians, and explaining their faith to LGBTQI+-aware clinicians. The cost was significant, and disengagement from care was a frequent consequence.
- **Inclusion, assumption and the limits of the tick-box.** EDI training that treats faith and LGBTQI+ identity as separate categories was repeatedly described as substituting for clinical conversation. Where clinicians had been told what a community ‘believes’, they often stopped asking the individual patient. Several participants described losing access to specific care (contraception, sexual health, screening) on the grounds that their faith was assumed to preclude the need.

- **Trust, proximity and clinicians from one's own community.** Encountering clinicians from one's own faith or cultural community was described as a continual risk assessment. A faith-shared clinician might understand cultural context but feel unsafe to come out to. A queer-friendly clinician might be ignorant of, or hostile to, the participant's faith. Participants described carrying out this internal risk assessment in every appointment.
- **Mental health.** The widest range of experience in the data. Participants who had used both NHS and private mental health services repeatedly described the latter as more able to engage faith and LGBTQI+ identity together, where NHS pathways tended to address one or the other in isolation, or neither.
- **Faith literacy.** Participants did not want clinicians to memorise more about a list of recognised faiths, particularly given that faith literacy training has been deployed in some cases to deny care to LGBTQI+ people of faith on the assumption that the faith precludes the request. They wanted clinicians to ask, with confidence and without performativity, and to recognise denominational diversity within traditions and faith identities outside the standard list of major religions.

Asked at the start of each session for a single word or short phrase capturing what came to mind about being LGBTQI+ and a person of faith in NHS healthcare, participants offered:

*noticed · invisible · conflicting · complicated · challenging ·
community · privacy · sexual health · why has it taken so long?*

Research priorities

Participants identified the following as the priority areas a larger study should examine:

- Sexual and reproductive health at the intersection of LGBTQI+ identity and faith, including for women and lesbian, bisexual and queer women specifically, where disaggregated data is largely absent.
- Conversion practices in healthcare settings, which remain legally permissible in parts of the UK and which participants raised as an under-researched and under-acknowledged risk.
- “Internal minorities” within faith communities, including LGBTQI+ people, women, disabled people and children, whose access to healthcare can be limited when faith authority is allowed to mediate clinical communication.
- The experience of trans people of faith in light of recent changes to NHS guidance, and the cumulative effect of institutional shifts on trust in services.
- Closeted people in heterosexual relationships within conservative faith communities, whose health needs and risks are largely absent from existing LGBTQI+ research framings.

- Faith literacy in clinical practice that goes beyond a fixed list of “major religions” and beyond singular denominational defaults.
- How EDI training is designed, who writes it, and whether it produces individualised care or new forms of stereotyping.

Methodological priorities

Asked how they would want to take part in a larger study at this intersection, and how they thought others like them would, participants identified the following design choices as material to whether they could meaningfully contribute:

- Multiple ways to take part, including focus groups, written submissions, one-to-one conversations and creative or visual methods.
- Cameras-off and pseudonymous participation as default options.
- Questions shared in advance, with thinking time built in.
- Transparent framing of what data is collected, how it is stored and who can see it.
- Recognition that participating is itself labour.

To ensure non-identifiability, recognisable characteristics not relevant to the quotes have been removed or altered with the permission of the participants. Quotations are attributed by participant code and no participant is named. The draft was reviewed by the Community Practitioner at The Faith & Belief Forum and by participants before publication.

Context

LGBTQI+ people in the UK continue to report discrimination and lower confidence in NHS healthcare (McDermott et al. 2021; Kneale et al. 2021). People of faith continue to report cultural and religious needs being misunderstood, ignored, or used against them in clinical settings (Dinham 2018; Mir et al. 2019). The two bodies of evidence rarely speak to each other, and the intersection of being both LGBTQI+ and a person of faith is largely unaddressed in UK health research. Almost nothing exists that has invited people at this intersection to define what that research should look at.

UK peer-reviewed studies focusing specifically on LGBTQI+ people of faith and their NHS healthcare experiences are largely absent. The implications of overlapping minoritised identities at this intersection, for clinical encounters specifically, remain unexplored. Participants in this project described a distinct configuration of risks, assumptions and silences that arises when both identities are present in the same clinical encounter, beyond what either body of evidence anticipates on its own.

Participants in this project repeatedly described navigating healthcare environments in which their LGBTQI+ identity and their faith identity were treated as if they could not coexist, or in which the assumed conflict between them was used to short-circuit clinical conversation altogether. Several described being ‘closeted’ in one or both directions, withholding their faith from LGBTQI+ services and their LGBTQI+ identity from faith-based clinicians, sometimes in the same week.

The project does not attempt to close that evidence gap. It asks the people most affected by it what a larger study should focus on, how it should be designed, and what they want it to lead to.

Methods

In line with the Birkbeck IFRC funding round, the project was delivered between April and May 2026. Recruitment was led by Sophie Mitchell, Senior Programmes Coordinator and LGBTQ+ Faith Lead at The Faith & Belief Forum, drawing on trusted community networks. Interest exceeded capacity twofold.

Two online focus groups were held on 29th April and 30th April 2026, each scheduled for up to two hours. Each participant was offered a 30-minute preparatory one-to-one conversation in advance to discuss consent, expectations and access needs. Sessions were audio recorded only, with participants free to use a chosen name, keep cameras off, and contribute through the chat or in writing afterwards. Participants who could not be accommodated in the focus groups were offered alternative routes: a one-to-one conversation with the lead researcher, or a written submission via an anonymous form that remained open after each session. Material from the one-to-ones and written submissions has been incorporated into this report alongside the focus group transcripts.

Sessions were structured loosely around three questions: what participants navigate in healthcare as LGBTQI+ people of faith; what assumptions they encounter; and what they would want a larger study to focus on. Facilitation was light, on the principle that participants should set the direction of conversation rather than answer a pre-formed schedule. Recordings were anonymised at the point of transcription and analysed thematically. The draft was reviewed by the Community Practitioner at the Faith & Belief Forum and then circulated to participants for amendment or removal of their contributions before finalisation.

Findings

Six themes recurred across the focus groups, one-to-one conversations and written submissions. Each theme describes how the two identities, LGBTQI+ and faith, interact within clinical encounters: how they shape what participants disclose, how clinicians respond to one or both, and where the system's categories struggle to accommodate them. Themes are presented in the order participants returned to them most heavily, beginning with sexual and reproductive health.

1. Sexual and reproductive health

Sexual and reproductive health was the most consistent area of return across both focus groups. It was raised as an opening word, returned to multiple times within each session, and named explicitly by several participants as the area they most wanted future research to address. The intersection of faith and LGBTQI+ identity was particularly visible here: faith framings of sex shaping participants' own ability to disclose; visible markers of faith shaping clinicians' willingness to take a sexual history; and operational categories within sexual health services unable to accommodate either dimension separately, let alone both together. One participant expressed:

"I'd want some research specifically on LGBTQ sexual healthcare: acceptance, shame, access, flexibility in treatment and support."

— P6

Three patterns recurred. The first was that NHS sexual health services were described as configured around two assumed populations: heterosexual couples, and gay men understood as a 'higher-risk' group. Lesbian, bisexual and queer women were repeatedly described as falling outside that operational frame. One participant described being told by her GP that the only way to access a sexual health clinic was to lie about her orientation, and being told by a clinician at the clinic itself:

"I cannot give you the care that you need today. Please complain. I back you 100 per cent, but I cannot give you the care that you need."

— clinician quoted by P3

Self-advocacy up to senior management level produced no change. The participant was told that lesbian women were "not a priority" and the service was not commissioned to provide care to them. Disaggregated data on women who have sex with women, including on HPV in this population, was described by another participant who has worked in NHS training as effectively

absent, with nurses delivering cervical screening training repeating the misinformation that lesbian women do not need to be screened.

The second pattern was assumption substituting for sexual history-taking. Where a participant's appearance triggered a default heteronormative reading, the question "are you sexually active" was either not asked at all, or was narrowed to a single script:

"I had to say, well, what do you mean by that? Because I'm with my partner. Well, is your partner female? Male. Okay, so are you having sex? To then go to my healthcare provider and feel invalidated because I'm not having the 'right type' of sex, it's really hurtful."

— P4

A participant who wears a hijab described being asked only "are you married", on the basis that the hijab was assumed to mean "prude", and being denied a clinically indicated intimate scan by a locum GP on the grounds of a hypothetical future husband's preference. Another participant described being raised in a faith tradition where sex outside marriage carried such weight that even arriving at sexual conversation with a clinician required active dismantling of internal shame, only to find the clinical conversation itself unable to accommodate her.

Several participants described compartmentalising their disclosure across services as a result. One Christian gay man shared that he uses NHS sexual health services but remains private with his GP about his sexuality. A Sikh gay man awaiting surgery described his specialist asking about a wife. He attributed the assumption to shared cultural background rather than to ill-will:

"Perhaps as they are from a similar cultural background, they have assumed that all men marry women. Not in my case. I have felt fearful as the specialist will be performing surgery on me over the coming months. I have evaded the subject until now and not confirmed my sexual identity."

— P23

His broader observation was that many people of faith may go 'back in the closet', or fail to correct staff, because of the effect that disclosure may have on their care. The same observation surfaced repeatedly across both groups.

The third pattern concerned privacy and gatekeeping in services for gay, bi and queer men. Participants described targeted public health campaigns that produced visible queues outside named venues, compromising privacy in small or interconnected faith communities:

"When there was the campaign and the scare around the monkeypox vaccine, lots of people were queueing. Sixty, seventy people queueing outside this particular venue. It was very uncomfortable, because I knew some of those people."

— P2

Participants raised concerns about gatekeeping within sexual health and HIV services. One described people being refused preventative medication on the grounds of insufficient sexual partners, and noted that women living with HIV remain largely absent from the service landscape. The persistence of HIV-related stigma was also raised in non-HIV clinical settings. One participant living with HIV recounted a dental appointment delayed over outdated requests for CD4 counts at a point when their viral load is undetectable. Another described an optical appointment in which the clinician’s instruments were inches from his face when the question came:

“How did you get HIV? I think the answer I give at that time depends if I’m going to walk out of that chair with my eyes intact.”

— P1

2. The burden of self-advocacy

Across nearly every account in both groups, participants described carrying the burden of being the person who has to do the work of being seen, understood, taken seriously, or referred onwards. At this intersection, the work was characteristically doubled: explaining their LGBTQI+ identity to faith-aware clinicians who assumed it could not coexist with their faith identity, and explaining their faith to LGBTQI+-aware clinicians who assumed it could not coexist with their LGBTQI+ identity. The self-advocacy showed up in different forms: deciding whether to come out, deciding which part to come out about, deciding whether the appointment was safer with both visible or with one of them concealed, correcting assumptions, escalating complaints up management chains to access basic services. It was described as constant, and largely invisible to the system that required it.

One participant put it:

“Having an awareness of LGBT health inequalities, being bi myself, and someone with faith, I am more aware. But that means that when I go into healthcare settings I am proactively advocating for myself, rather than the healthcare provider being conscientious and aware and initiating relevant conversations with me. I’m having to do the burden of that work.”

— P4

The advocacy was not optional. Several participants described losing access to care entirely when they did not push, did not escalate, did not lie about their orientation, did not take their case to senior management, or did not bring an MP into correspondence with a hospital chief executive. Where the system failed to ask the relevant question, the question did not get asked. Where the patient could not bear to keep advocating, the care simply did not happen.

One participant framed self-advocacy as a community-organisation responsibility, in the absence of statutory provision:

“If there’s no self-advocacy for these women, there will be no services at all.”

— P22

Several participants linked the cumulative weight of self-advocacy to disengagement from care altogether. Where the cost of being known felt too high, or the energy to advocate had been spent elsewhere, participants described not seeking care, withholding parts of their history from clinicians, or not pursuing complaints when they had cause.

Asked who in the focus group had made a formal complaint to the NHS about an experience related to faith, LGBTQI+ identity or both, half the room raised their hands. Asked who had had cause but had not gone ahead, the rest raised their hands. Every participant had encountered something they considered worth reporting.

Where a complaint was pursued, the system did not always recognise the substance of what was being raised. One participant described attending A&E repeatedly with severe pelvic pain (later identified as a gynaecological condition) and being triaged each time under a new open-door policy in which the cubicle door remained open during clinical conversations, including questions about pregnancy and sexual activity. Asked whether she was sexually active by a nurse who refused to close the door, she said no, partly because she had no idea who could hear on the other side. She believed pain relief had been withheld over an hour while clinicians sought to rule out pregnancy, and that more open disclosure on her part might have changed the timeline. Her formal complaint was rebuffed: the hospital cited GDPR and operational efficiency, and noted that further measures to enforce the policy were planned. Her observation:

“Coming from a religious background, the stigma and shame associated with sexual activity basically comes prepackaged. So when you add to that queer identities and the potential for stigma there, you end up withholding info that could be crucial to your care.”

— P24

The episode draws together several patterns described in this report: a clinical setting whose physical and policy design assumed disclosure would be straightforward, the interaction of religious framings of sex with clinicians’ ability to ask honestly, the cost to care of a single inhibition (in this case, an open door), and a complaints process that defended the policy rather than the patient.

3. Inclusion, assumption and the limits of the tick-box

A coherent and shared conceptual thread ran through both focus groups concerning the way that current EDI and inclusion approaches were producing harm. Participants did not frame this as a complaint about training in principle. They described training, applied uncritically, being used to substitute for clinical conversation, where clinicians told that a specific community holds a particular position concluded that there is no need to ask the patient in front of them.

A participant captured the dynamic in a phrase that several others picked up:

“After having my child, a midwife said to me, your community don’t use contraception, so I’m not going to ask you about it. She’d received training that told her to see me in a certain light. It just reduces us to a tick box.”

— P3

She continued:

“By creating these lists, we now have people who are not on the list, or people who make the list too complicated. Personally, I feel like a victim of inclusivity. Bad inclusivity.”

— P3

Another participant shared the sentiment, noting:

“We’re going to be blanket inclusive, which means we aren’t inclusive at all. Inclusivity should be a trigger for further conversation, learning and dialogue.”

— P21

And another added:

“I agree, it’s performative inclusivity. Assumptions seem to be the word, so many assumptions.”

— P20

A participant extended the argument to populations whose sexual lives do not map onto the LGBTQI+ identity categories researchers and clinicians use:

“There’s a whole experience which is closeted people in heterosexual marriages, having other kinds of sex outside their marriage, super stigmatised, hiding from their healthcare provider. Assumptions shouldn’t exclude people who don’t use an LGBT identity to describe sexual contact they’re having.”

— P14

The pattern was not confined to faith. Participants described assumptions made on the basis of ethnicity (a participant of South Asian background investigated for tuberculosis on the basis of geography rather than symptoms; another assumed to have a particular dietary and risk profile on the basis of community membership); on the basis of name and visible markers (a participant assumed to be a migrant seeking asylum on the basis of their first name); on the basis of body size (a participant whose treatment options were narrowed because, as their clinician put it, she was overweight).

Trans participants described two reciprocal versions of the same dynamic. Where a faith identity was visible (through an ordained title, for example), the conversation often shifted into questioning the participant’s right to hold both identities at once, with their actual clinical needs

receding from view. Where the trans identity was visible first, faith was assumed away: chaplaincy services were not offered, and surprise was registered when the participant asked to see a chaplain. Both patterns made the clinical encounter contingent on the participant's ability to manage the clinician's reaction to one or other axis of their identity.

An additional pattern, raised by another participant, was that public health communication mediated through faith authority figures could itself become a vector of exclusion. They described an NHS training event addressed by a religious figure on how to communicate the HPV vaccine to women in his community, on the basis that marketing should only be approved by religious leadership and only directed at married women. The participant's observation was that internal minorities within faith communities, including LGBTQI+ people, women, disabled people and children, pay the cost when faith authority is allowed to mediate clinical communication. This is a separate but related issue to tick-box inclusion: where inclusion was seen to fail by flattening, faith-authority mediation was seen to fail by deferring.

4. Trust, proximity and clinicians from one's own community

Participants in both groups returned repeatedly to the experience of encountering clinicians who shared their faith, ethnicity or community background. The accounts were consistently double-edged. Familiarity could mean shared reference points and reduced explanatory burden, or it could mean a real and immediate threat of exposure to people connected to one's family or community.

A participant described travelling between cities for sexual health and HIV-related care to avoid being seen by people they knew. Another participant echoed this tension:

"It's a double-edged sword. They might be more sensitive to things specific to my faith, but I also don't feel safe being out to them. A middle ground is sometimes seeing other clinicians of colour who aren't part of my community directly but have proximity to it."

— P7

The risk could run in either direction. A participant in FG2 described coming out to a hijabi clinician of her own background during a procedure:

"She made a face when I said I'm gay. It was kind of invalidating that part of my identity, but also kind of saying, you know, you're observing your faith. She sort of took turns with invalidating different parts of me."

— P16

Another participant described the practical cost of a community-based GP sharing their faith but having an approach that did not extend to trans-affirming treatment. It was described as a long-standing community practice, with all the trust that came with the family relationship to it, but unable to provide the medication needed. The participant had to switch to a practice with

“secular doctors”, with the loss of context that entailed. One participant raised a serious related point about safeguarding in faith-community medical settings, observing that doctors hold a position of trust within tight-knit communities that can amplify harm where it occurs.

Participants were clear that none of this meant clinicians from one’s own community should be avoided. However, it was expressed that the patient is the only person in a position to know whether a particular community-based encounter is safe, and is doing this risk assessment each time without support in that setting.

5. Mental health

Mental health services produced the widest range of experience in the data. Several participants described positive encounters in which a clinician had taken time to understand the whole person, including faith and sexual orientation together. Others described the inverse: time-pressured pathways in which neither dimension was discussed, group settings in which disclosure felt unsafe, and at least one serious confidentiality breach that had eroded a participant’s trust in primary care for years afterwards.

A trans Jewish participant described an early experience in which the counsellor learning of their Jewish identity had then deployed “biblical metaphors” throughout the session that they had not asked for. Another described a clear contrast between private and NHS mental health care:

“I’ve had a much more positive experience with private mental health care, because of the time taken to understand someone as a whole person. With NHS mental health care, the peoplehood is stripped out. It’s, okay, let’s just refer you to CBT, refer you on this pathway.”

— P10

Several participants noted that group settings in mental health pathways were particularly difficult, with disclosure feeling impossible in rooms where they could not assess the safety of every other person present. Conversely, one-to-one settings where the clinician had time and curiosity could be among the better experiences participants had reported. Participants also raised, here and elsewhere, the cumulative emotional toll of self-advocacy, disclosure and partial concealment. The intersection of LGBTQI+ identity and faith was described as something that had to be carried, and the carrying itself had mental health consequences that the system did not register.

6. Faith literacy and the limits of training

Participants described clinicians who did not recognise their faith, who placed it within a more familiar tradition, or who did not know enough about the relevant practices to ask useful questions. Across both groups, participants distinguished sharply between two ways of understanding faith literacy. The first was knowing the right things about a list of recognised

faiths. The second was being equipped to ask. Participants were uniformly clear that the second was what they wanted, and that the first was producing many of the harms described elsewhere in this report.

Pagan participants described NHS guidance treating paganism as functionally synonymous with Wicca, leaving other beliefs unrecognised at the level of the system's own categories. A participant from a goddess-centred tradition described carrying a faith that most clinicians did not recognise as a faith at all. A participant from a Mormon background described facing repeated incredulity at her not drinking and not smoking, with clinicians pressing the point as if her stated practice were implausible.

Several participants noted that even within recognised traditions, denominational diversity was systematically flattened. A trans Jewish participant noted that on-site chaplaincy in his hospital had been Orthodox-funded, raising the question of whether his identity would be welcome there. Another participant described being treated as if her relationship to her faith could be read from the visible marker she wore, when in practice the relationship was contested, evolving and personal.

Participants were clear that they were not asking clinicians to memorise more denominations:

"I'm talking less about things that might be on offer to support people of faith, and more about what people of faith might need to access in line with universal delivery. Not super radical, asking to access contraception."

— P13

Participants distinguished the two routes clearly. One participant disagreed with another's call for more denomination-specific knowledge, on the grounds that knowing this community holds that practice could itself be deployed to deny care. Better, several argued, to train clinicians in the practice of asking, including practice exercises that gave them confidence to ask without performance:

"If you have a healthcare practitioner who recognises it is really important to ask questions in an inclusive way, but they've never had the chance to practise it, they're going to be nervous, going to shy away and be vague."

— P15

Research priorities

Participants identified the following as priorities for a larger piece of research, framed as questions a larger study should be able to answer. The priorities below map directly to the six findings set out above, with two further priorities (priorities 7 and 8) reflecting cross-cutting concerns that participants raised across multiple themes. The priorities are not ranked.

1. Sexual and reproductive health at the intersection

A larger study should examine how LGBTQI+ people of faith access sexual and reproductive health services in the NHS, and what is happening at the points where they cannot. Participants want this to include:

- The sexual health of women, including lesbian, bisexual, queer and trans women, where existing data is sparse and disaggregation is largely absent.
- HPV, cervical screening and other women’s sexual-health conditions, particularly the question of how clinicians communicate risk and screening eligibility to women whose sexual histories do not fit their operational categories.
- The pathways by which gay, bi and queer men access sexual-health services in ways that compromise privacy in small or interconnected faith communities.
- The treatment of long-living people with HIV in non-HIV settings (dental, optical, primary care), where stigma and outdated practice were repeatedly described.
- The interaction of religious framings of sex (shame, silence, marriage as the only legitimate context) with clinicians’ ability to take an accurate sexual history.
- The persistence of conversion practices in or adjacent to UK healthcare settings, which remain legally permissible in some forms and which participants raised as a concrete, current concern. The study should consider how clinicians are trained to recognise conversion practices, what safeguards exist, and what duty-of-care frameworks apply.

2. The cumulative effect of self-advocacy

A larger study should examine the cumulative effect, on people at multiple intersecting minoritised identities, of being the people who have to translate themselves into the system. Participants described this work as constant and largely unrecognised. The study should consider how it affects help-seeking, trust, and willingness to engage with healthcare and with research, including the proportion of people who experience cause for complaint but do not pursue it.

3. Inclusion, assumption and the design of EDI training

A larger study should examine how equality, diversity and inclusion training in the NHS is currently designed, who writes it, and whether it is producing individualised care or a new generation of stereotypes. Participants were clear that some of the worst experiences they reported came not from clinicians who lacked training, but from clinicians who had been trained and were applying that training in ways that flattened rather than informed their practice. The study should consider, in particular, whether training includes practice elements that give clinicians the confidence to ask questions in real consultations rather than retreating into vagueness.

A related sub-question concerns how clinical and public-health communication is mediated through faith communities. Participants raised the risk that, where the NHS routes communication through recognised community spokespeople, ‘internal minorities’ (LGBTQI+ people, women, disabled people, children) lose access to direct address. The study should explicitly include voices that are not reachable through the standard route of the recognised community representative.

A separate suggestion was that the NHS should consider quality-mark recognition for departments and hospitals that demonstrate good practice in this area, on the basis that visible recognition can be a motivator in its own right.

4. Trust, community clinicians and confidentiality

A larger study should examine how LGBTQI+ people of faith navigate clinical encounters with practitioners from their own faith or cultural community, and how confidentiality is protected (or compromised) in primary care, sexual health and emergency settings. Participants described the patient as the only person in a position to assess whether a community-based encounter was safe, and described doing this work without support. The study should consider what would change if the system shared more of that load, and what design choices in clinical settings (open-door triage policies, shared-language clinical lists, named-clinician booking) interact with confidentiality at this intersection.

5. Mental health

A larger study should examine the mental health experiences of LGBTQI+ people of faith in NHS care, with particular attention to the contrast between time-pressured pathways in which neither dimension can be discussed, and the small number of encounters in which a clinician engaged the whole person. Participants who had used both NHS and private mental health services described the latter as more able to hold faith and LGBTQI+ identities together. The study should consider what is lost when the NHS cannot, and how group settings, confidentiality protections and matched-clinician pathways affect engagement.

6. Faith literacy in clinical practice

A larger study should examine how clinicians are equipped to engage with the faith dimension of patients' lives. Participants were specific: they did not want clinicians to be expected to memorise more denominations, but to ask. The study should consider what good faith literacy looks like in practice, including how to ask without performance, how to recognise denominational diversity within a single tradition, and how to engage with faith and belief identities that fall outside the standard list of major religions.

7. Trans people of faith and the changing institutional landscape

A larger study should examine how recent changes to NHS guidance for trans people are interacting with the experiences of trans people who also hold a faith identity. This was raised as a live concern in both groups, and as a reason that some participants were avoiding NHS contact. The 2025 Supreme Court ruling on single-sex spaces was named in a written submission as a reason trans participants in the submitter's wider network were avoiding hospital contact, fearing being placed on a ward not aligning with their gender. The study should consider what trans people of faith are now navigating, and the cumulative effect of recent institutional shifts on trust in NHS services.

8. Populations missing from current LGBTQI+ research framings

A larger study should also examine populations who fall outside the standard LGBTQI+ research framings but whose experiences are shaped by the same intersection. Two such groups were named in the data. The first is people whose sexual or romantic lives do not match the LGBTQI+ identity categories that current research uses, and who are 'closeted' within heterosexual relationships and conservative faith communities. One participant described environments in which same-sex contact occurs without being framed as gay, alongside marriages whose participants would not describe themselves through an LGBTQI+ lens. This group is largely missing from current LGBTQI+ research framings, and is at particular risk of disclosure-driven harm in clinical settings.

The second group raised by participants is LGBTQI+ people of faith whose communities are tightly bounded enough that disclosure within them is genuinely unsafe, and who are therefore unreachable through community spokespeople or recognised representatives. Future research should explicitly include voices that are not reachable through the standard route, and should consider how recruitment design either enables or forecloses access to these populations.

Methodological priorities

Participants were asked how they would want to input into a larger study at this intersection, and how they thought others like them would want to take part. Their reflections covered who would feel able to come forward, what would lower the threshold of participation, and what kinds of involvement would feel meaningful rather than tokenistic. The methodological priorities below draw on what participants said directly, on the design choices that visibly worked or failed in the sessions themselves, and on participants' specific suggestions for reaching others within their communities who were not in the room.

Multiple ways to participate

Future research should offer focus groups, one-to-one conversations, written submissions and creative or arts-based methods, and let participants choose. Several participants spoke specifically in favour of creative or visual methods:

"I mentioned art therapy earlier. It would be amazing if there was a chance to engage through something more creative or artistic, and then have the opportunity to talk about it. But I don't know if that's too social for a research thing."

— P16

"Video, because video is probably one of the most effective medias, especially if you're getting someone's story. It makes it a lot more personal."

— P8

"Community pride events could be interesting. There might also be some room for more creativity about doing boards or installations or different projects."

— P17

Others were clear that focus groups carried unique value because of the experience of being in the room with other people at the same intersection.

Camera-off and pseudonymous participation

Several participants joined with cameras off, used chosen names rather than legal names, and were explicit that this was what allowed them to take part at all:

"I've actually come to a friend's house to have this conversation, because I can't have it at home safely. Having multiple options for people who aren't out, or who aren't visible, is helpful."

— P16

Future research must treat pseudonymous and camera-off participation as a fully legitimate route, rather than an exception that needs to be negotiated.

Sharing questions in advance

Knowing the questions in advance would have allowed several participants to recall instances from earlier in their lives that did not surface in the moment:

“Having the questions in advance might give people just some more time to mull over things, and to maybe think of a few instances that happened a few years ago that have been forgotten.”

— P17

Future research should circulate questions ahead of sessions, allow time for written responses afterwards, and be open about the fact that some of the most important contributions are likely to come hours or days after the session ends, as opposed to within it.

Data and confidentiality

Participants were attentive to questions of how their data would be used, who could see it, and what would happen to it. One participant raised, explicitly, concerns about institutional data collection on minoritised identities given the changing political climate:

“I may not choose to reveal my own plans, or put it down anywhere on paper, that I’m Jewish. I may be more sceptical of how my information is used by institutions.”

— P17

Future research should be transparent about data handling at every stage, and should be designed to allow participants to contribute without producing institutional records they cannot later control.

Including healthcare professionals as research participants

One participant suggested that future research should also ask healthcare professionals what one thing they could change to make the experience of LGBTQI+ people of faith more positive. The reasoning was that an open-ended question would surface different answers from a closed survey, and would engage clinicians as agents rather than as objects of study:

“When people fill out questionnaires, they think about what the answer might be out there, what’s the status quo. But if they were asked what they would do, then they’ve got to give some more thought to that.”

— P18

There was a sense from multiple participants that a co-located conversation between LGBTQI+ people of faith and clinicians would not be useful:

“I don’t think anything can be benefited by getting health professionals in a room with us, because the health professionals that will come are those that are already sensitive to these issues. You’d never get those who really need to consider the internal bias they may have.”

— P19

Trauma-informed approach

Participants were clear that future research at this intersection should be underpinned by trauma-informed principles. Participants raised experiences including disclosure-driven harm, confidentiality breaches, religious harm, and clinical encounters at the limit of bodily safety. Research design should anticipate this, build in pacing and pause points, offer multiple modes of contribution (including written submissions for material participants are not ready to speak aloud), and ensure participants have ongoing control over what of their contribution is used and how.

Recognition and payment

Participants were paid an honorarium in line with NIHR public involvement guidance. This was both noticed and appreciated, but the cost of participating, in emotional labour, in disclosure, and in the compounding work of self-advocacy, exceeds the honorarium. Future research should pay at NIHR rates as a minimum and should design sessions in ways that minimise unnecessary additional labour. Optional draft-review work, for instance, should be opt-in and recognised as further work.

Genuine co-production

Several participants indicated that they would like to be involved as co-applicants or co-producers in any future funded study, partly to ensure that others at this intersection do not have to navigate what they have, on condition that co-production was genuine: shaping research questions rather than being consulted on them, named community co-applicants as a real route, and ongoing involvement paid.

Implications for practice

Several practice-level points emerged with sufficient clarity to be reported here, alongside the priority-setting work. They are offered to clinicians, commissioners and training designers as observations from people with lived experience.

- Asking is almost always better than assuming. The clinical instinct to apply training-derived assumptions to the patient in front of you is producing care that is worse, not better, for people at this intersection.
- EDI training that flattens a community into a single practice can produce harm. Clinicians cite the training in support of withholding care, often in good faith, and the patient bears the cost.
- Sexual health services configured around heterosexual couples and gay men are excluding lesbian, bisexual and queer women, and women of faith specifically. The exclusion is operational.
- HIV stigma in non-HIV clinical settings, including dental and optical care, remains a live problem. Updates to clinical training on viral suppression and undetectable status have not reached parts of the system where people living with HIV regularly attend.
- Trust is contextual. A clinician from a patient's own community can be a positive presence or a serious risk, and the patient is the only person in a position to know which.
- Faith literacy depends less on memorising denominational detail and more on willingness to ask. Clinicians who are trained to ask, with confidence and without performance, will provide better care than clinicians who are trained to know.

About the project

Faith in Practice was funded by Birkbeck, University of London, through its Wellcome Trust-supported Institutional Funding for Research Culture programme, under the Nothing About Us Without Us seed-funding scheme. The project ran from April to May 2026 and was led by Dr Daniella Shaw at Birkbeck. Recruitment and community partnership were led by Sophie Mitchell at the Faith & Belief Forum, who also reviewed the draft. Carrie Alderton, CEO of the Faith & Belief Forum, provided advisory input.

The findings will inform a larger collaborative research application in late 2026. Participants who indicated interest will be invited to be involved on agreed terms.

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- Mir, G., Ghani, R., Meer, S. and Hussain, G. (2019) Delivering a culturally adapted therapy for Muslim clients with depression. *The Cognitive Behaviour Therapist*, 12, p.e26.
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Further reading

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Examines how GPs understand 'spirituality' and how they apply the concept in consultations with patients.
- Bachmann, C.L. and Gooch, B. (2018) *LGBT in Britain: Health Report*. London: Stonewall.
Reports survey findings on the frequency with which LGBT people in the UK encounter discrimination from health staff and avoid care as a result.
- Bachmann, C.L. and Gooch, B. (2018) *LGBT in Britain: Trans Report*. London: Stonewall.
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The largest UK survey of LGBT people's lives, with over 108,000 responses, covering healthcare experiences and disclosure to staff.

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Reviews the materials used to train UK health and social care staff about caring for LGBT+ patients, and assesses their scope and quality.

Kneale, D. and Bécares, L. (2021) Discrimination as a predictor of poor mental health among LGBTQ+ people during the COVID-19 pandemic: cross-sectional analysis of the online Queerantime study. *BMJ Open*, 11(6), p.e049405.

Finds that poor mental health among LGBTQ+ people during the pandemic was predicted by experiences of discrimination rather than by identity itself.

Kneale, D. and Bécares, L. (2024) The influence of a hostile environment on a syndemic of depression, stress and chronic limiting illness among LGBTQ+ people during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 46(1), pp.114-136.

Attributes the poor health LGBTQ+ people experienced during the pandemic to a hostile social climate rather than to identity itself, and traces how the resulting stress connects worse mental and physical health.

Kohli, M., Reeves, I. and Waters, L. (2024) Homophobia in the provision of sexual health care in the UK. *The Lancet HIV*, 11(2), pp.e125-e130.

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LGBT Foundation (2020) *Hidden Figures: LGBT Health Inequalities in the UK*. Manchester: LGBT Foundation.

A life-course overview of LGBT health inequalities, drawing on published research and the charity's own service data.

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Woolf Institute (2024) *Faith in Mental Health*. Cambridge: Woolf Institute.

Reports a two-year project on Muslim communities and NHS mental health, arguing for care that engages with people's faith.